

15-17, and 24-28 K.K. region assignable⁴ to $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transition respectively. Extinction coefficient values are low in conformity with octahedral environment. Comparison of the bands with the solid state reflectance spectra of one representative compound indicates a little dissociation of the ligands in spite of the added base as the bands in solution spectra are at lower energy. It is quite probable that there is a distortion of the octahedron in solution as the two nitrogen ligands are in transposition. Hence the complexes have presumably a spin-free octahedral configuration on the basis of their analysis, magnetic moments and electronic spectral data.

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Mercury Complexes of Sulphonamides

G. S. MISRA and M. V. RAMAKRISHNA RAO

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research
in Chemistry, University of Jabalpur,
Jabalpur(M.P.)

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MISRA *et al*¹⁻³ and Shukla *et al*⁴ have reported the cyanoethylation of a large number of sulphonamides. Such cyanoethylated compounds form complexes with mercuric ion with great facility⁵. Recently sulphonamides were used as a complexing agent for various metals⁶ and it was shown by bacteriostatic studies that these complexes are more potent than the parent drugs⁷.

The present communication deals with the study of complexes of some more substituted sulphonamides and cyanoethylated sulphonamides with mercury (II) chloride.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes :

The cyanoethylated sulphanilamides were prepared according to the method of Misra *et al*³.

All the complexes reported were prepared by refluxing a calculated amount of the sulphonamide and mercuric chloride in absolute alcohol. An alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide was added to the

refluxing mixture until the pH remained constant at approx. 8. Refluxing was continued for 2-3 hr. The product obtained was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The quantitative estimation of mercury, chlorine and sulphur was done by the usual methods, viz., mercury volumetrically by titration with thiocyanate⁸, chlorine gravimetrically as AgCl and sulphur gravimetrically as BaSO₄. Conductivity measurements were carried out in nitrobenzene with a conductivity bridge (Philips). Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Grating Infrared Spectrophotometer (Model-177). The results of the chemical analysis are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were quite stable and were found to be insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, viz., benzene, diethyl ether, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and acetone. They are sparingly soluble in nitrobenzene. The analytical results reveal that the ligand and metal are in equimolecular ratio (1 : 1). The low molar conductance shows that these complexes are non-electrolytic in nature⁹. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes shows that the halogen atoms are also bonded to mercury with its inner coordination sphere. This gives coordination number four in all the complexes.

The infrared spectra of the ligand as well as their complexes have been examined. Only the important sites in the sulphanilamide and cyanoethylated sulphanilamide, viz., —NH— and —C≡N groups have been taken into account.

—NH— of the sulphanilamide has two sharp bands at 3380 and 3480 cm⁻¹ owing to the symmetric and N—H stretching vibrations. These bands of —NH— group shift to a lower frequency region in the complexes. As both the —NH₂ groups in the sulphanilamide molecule have a lone pair of electrons, it may be concluded the two NH₂ groups are attached to the two mercury giving a dimeric species, which also explains the insolubility of the complex. A tentative structure of the complex is given in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

TABLE 1 EXPERIMENTAL DATA OF MERCURY COMPLEXES OF SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDES

Serial No.	Compounds	% Mercury Found (Calcd.)	% Chlorine Found (Calcd.)	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)
1.	Dichloro-(sulphanilamide) mercury II	45.50 (45.23)	16.00 (16.01)	7.20 (7.21)
2.	Dichloro-(sulphapyridine) mercury II	38.51 (38.48)	13.20 (13.61)	6.60 (6.14)
3.	Dichloro-(sulphathiazole) mercury II	37.74 (38.09)	12.99 (13.48)	12.50 (12.15)
4.	Dichloro-(sulphadiazine) mercury II	38.70 (38.48)	14.14 (13.61)	6.00 (6.14)
5.	Dichloro-(sulphamerazine) mercury II	37.78 (38.31)	13.48 (13.56)	6.00 (6.11)
6.	Dichloro-(sulphadimidine) mercury II	35.96 (36.42)	12.49 (12.89)	6.01 (5.81)
7.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphanilamide) mercury II	36.04 (36.5)	13.00 (12.92)	5.10 (5.74)
8.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphapyridine) mercury II	34.75 (34.90)	12.64 (12.36)	6.01 (5.57)
9.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphathiazole) mercury II	34.23 (34.60)	12.50 (12.25)	11.60 (11.04)
10.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphadiazine) mercury II	35.20 (34.90)	12.50 (12.36)	5.10 (5.57)
11.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphamerazine) mercury II	35.01 (34.78)	12.62 (12.34)	6.10 (5.55)
12.	Dichloro-(cyanoethyl sulphadimidine) mercury II	33.50 (33.29)	12.30 (11.79)	5.79 (5.31)

In the cyanoethylated sulphanilamide, the band observed at 2260 cm^{-1} corresponds to the —C=N stretching band. The bands at 3380 and 3500 cm^{-1} are due to the —NH— group. In the complex, these bands due to $\text{—C}\equiv\text{N}$ as well as —NH— group shift to a lower frequency which may be attributed to the coordination effect. A dimeric species, as in the case of sulphanilamide, can be postulated to be existing in cyanoethylated sulphanilamide. A plausible structure for the complex has been put forward in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

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